

Studies in Fluorinated 1,3-Diketones and Related Compounds, Part VII[†] : Mass Spectra of Some New Fluorinated Cu(II) 1,3-Diketonates

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The mass spectra of seven new fluorinated Cu(II) 1,3-diketonates of the general structure, L_2Cu (where L is a fluorinated 1,3-diketone anion) have been recorded and discussed. These spectra show some preferential fragmentation pattern, (except compd. No. 7), the most striking characteristic being the stepwise removal of alkyl/perfluoroalkyl substituents. Substitution of alkyl group by perfluoroalkyl group in these chelates lead to more extensive fragmentation of the molecular ions. Migration of hydrogen atom has been observed in some of the fragments. The loss of $\cdot F$, $\cdot CF_3$, $\cdot C_2F_5$ and $\cdot CH_3$ radicals has been observed from molecular ion, and may be interpreted as due to vinylic cleavage. A few doubly charged ions have also been observed. In all cases the base peak is due to $ArCO^+$. A number of noteworthy metastable peaks due to transitions such as $(L_2Cu-R)^+ \rightarrow (L_2Cu-2R)^+$ and $Ar-C \equiv O^+ \rightarrow Ar^+$ are observed. All chelates exhibit a strong peak due to L^+ , the formation of which may be attributed to a valence change of bivalent to univalent state such as $L_2Cu^+ \rightarrow L^+ + LCu$.

MASS spectrometry of metal 1,3-diketonates has received considerable attention as well as controversy, during the last decade. The pioneering studies of McDonald and Shannon¹ on transition metal complexes, containing 1,1-diketone ligands opened a new era in the chemistry of metal 1,3-diketonates. Later on, a number of workers²⁻⁹ reported the mass spectroscopic studies of acetylacetonates, 1,3-diketonates of first transition metals, metal chelates of dibenzoylmethane and lanthanide complexes of hexamethylacetylacetonate. The mass spectral studies of hexafluoroacetylacetonates and trifluoroacetylacetonates of Al(III), Fe(III), Fe(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with particular reference to their appearance potentials for major ions, were reported by Westmore *et al.*^{10,12}

In continuation of our recent work on fluorinated 1,3-diketones and related compounds, we have synthesised a number of Cu(II) chelates of some new fluorinated 1,3-diketones prepared by us.¹² We now report a comprehensive mass spectral study of seven new Cu(II) fluorinated 1,3-diketonates (Fig 1) and a comparison of our results with the findings of previous workers.

(Fig 1)

Compound No.	Ar	R [†]
1	2,5-Difluorophenyl	CF ₃
2	3-Fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl	CF ₃
3	2,5-Difluorophenyl	CH ₃
4	3-Fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl	CH ₃
5	2,5-Difluorophenyl	C ² F ₅
6	4-Fluorophenyl	C ² F ₅
7	3-Fluoro-4-methoxyphenyl	C ³ H ₅

Experimental

Preparation of fluorinated 1,3-diketones : The fluorinated 1,3-diketones used in this study, have been prepared by the method of Jcshi *et al.*¹³

Preparation of Copper(II) 1,3-diketonates : The

[†] For Part VI in the series see K. C. Joshi, V. N. Pathak and K. R. Kumawat, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1977, 1127.

copper(II) 1,3-diketonates used in this study, have been prepared by the methods of Joshi *et al.*¹³

Mass spectra—The mass spectra were recorded on a CEC 21-110B mass spectrometer, operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV. The source temperature was maintained at 200-300°, depending upon the volatility of the chelates.

Results and Discussion

The removal of an electron from metal 1,3-diketonates is believed to take place either from a molecular orbital localised mainly on the metal⁷ or from a molecular orbital localized mainly on the π -system of the ligand.⁷

In earlier studies⁹⁻¹¹, the role of metal was generally considered to be important. It was mentioned that the divalent and trivalent derivatives of a given 1,3-diketone show ionization potentials (I. P.) falling in a limited range, irrespective of the electronic configuration of the central metal atom. Bonati *et al.*¹⁴ have examined the ionization energies of a number of rhodium and iridium 1,3-diketonates with special reference to the nature of the highest occupied orbital. They have also measured the first ionization energies of a number of $(CO)_2M$ (1,3-diketone) complexes by electron impact and proposed that the molecular orbital is not localized on the π -system of the chelate ring, but delocalized as a whole and has a significant participation of metal atomic orbitals. They have also noticed that the important features of the mass spectra are being influenced by the nature of both the chelate ring as well as the central metal atom.

However, in the present study, we have observed some very interesting doubly charged ions e.g. $(L_2Cu)^{2+}$ and $(L_2Cu-R)^{2+}$ which are most probably formed by loss of one electron from each chelate ring. No such observation has been reported by previous workers.

In contrast to the results reported by Belchar *et al.*¹⁵ for alkaline earth chelates, we have observed more abundant molecular ions in the mass spectra of copper chelates. The most striking features of the mass spectra of these complexes are the large number of fragments containing copper. The important fragments which have isotopic copper are L_2Cu^+ , $(L_2Cu-F)^+$, $(L_2Cu-R)^+$, $(L_2Cu-2R)^+$, $(L_2Cu-L)^+$, $(LCu-F)^+$, $(L_2Cu-H_2)^+$, $(L_2Cu-CF)^+$, $(LCu-R)^+$ and ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu . These fragments are easily identified with the help of the isotopic abundance of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu .

In the present study we have noticed that substitution of alkyl group by prefluoroalkyl group leads to more extensive fragmentation of the molecular ion under electron impact. The greater fragmentation of fluorinated chelates, is ascribed to (1) relative instability of the molecular ion due to

weak C-perfluoroalkyl bond in the molecular ion, (II) relative stability of fragmented ions, some of which rearrange allowing formation of strong metal-fluorine bonds, and (III) destabilization of a C-CF₃ or C-C₂F₅ band owing to the increased positive charge on carbon atom.^{10,11}

We have observed two fragmentation pathways in which the parent ion eliminates alkyl/perfluoroalkyl groups stepwise (Scheme-A) or the ligand (Scheme-B). All important ions with their *m/e* values and relative intensities (%) are given in the Table 1.

Scheme-A: The mass spectral data show a clear fragmentation pattern involving the stepwise elimination of alkyl or perfluoroalkyl groups from the chelate ring. The formation of $(L_2Cu-F)^+$ (17) and $(L_2Cu-alkyl/perfluoroalkyl)^+(7)$ ions from molecular ion $(L_2Cu)^+$ (1), have been observed in the mass spectra of all the chelate studied. The next step of the fragmentation is the formation of ion 8, by loss of one alkyl or perfluoroalkyl radical from the ion 7. The fragmentation is confirmed by appropriate metastable peaks (Table 2).

The strong peak due to L^+ observed in all the cases may be attributed to a valence change of copper ion from bivalent to univalent state. Similar valency changes have been observed by other workers.^{5,7,10,11,16-19}

The presence of ion $CuAr^+$, in the mass spectra of all the chelates, indicates migration of the aromatic group¹³. Migration of trifluoromethyl group to copper is also confirmed by observing a suitable metastable peak of the transition $(LCuCF_3^+ \rightarrow CuCF_3 + L^+)$.

In addition to the stepwise elimination of two alkyl/perfluoroalkyl groups, two molecules of CO are successively eliminated from ion 8 to yield ions 9 and 10 (These ions have been observed only in the case of compound nos. 3 and 4 at *m/e* 399 and 423 for ion (9) and at *m/e* 371 and 395 for ion

(10), respectively. Elimination of one $ArC = C-H$ and one $ArCO$ moieties from ion (10) yields $CuCH^+$ (14). Other possible fragmentations of the molecular ion have been summarized in Scheme-A. Fragmentation of HL^+ and L^+ are similar, the first step in both cases is the elimination of alkyl/perfluoroalkyl radical to yield $[ArCOCH_2CO]^+$ (21) and $[ArCOCHCO]^+$ (22) moieties, respectively. The ion $Ar-C \equiv O^+$ (23) is the base peak in the mass spectra of all the chelates studied. This highly stable ion may be derived directly from the molecular ion, the ligand or any of the ions containing the $ArCO$ -unit.

Aromatic fluorine atom is generally eliminated

in the form of neutral HF molecule from ions containing Ar-unit.

Scheme-B: The molecular ion has acyclic structure (1). The migration of a hydrogen radical from one β -diketonate portion to another portion leads to the rearranged molecular ion (3) which undergoes fragmentation in two ways. The elimination of one HL yields the ion (9) and there is a valency change of copper from Cu(II) \rightarrow Cu(I) [as shown in ions (9) and (10)]^{12,16-19}. The transition $L_2Cu^+ \rightarrow (LCu-H)^+ + HL$ has been confirmed by observation of appropriate metastable peak for compound No. 4. The loss of $RCOCCOAr$ from ion (3) yield $LCuH^+$ ion (5). The ions $[RCOCCOAr]^+$ (11) and $[ArCOCCO]^+$ (12) are also obtained.

In contrast to the fragmentation patterns for compound Nos. 1-6, we have not observed stepwise

fragmentation of aryl radicals in case of compound No. 7, which contains two phenyl groups. Apart from molecular ion L_2Cu^+ (at m/e value 605), we have observed only $[L_2Cu-(C_6H_5+FC_6H_4OCH_3)]^+$, $[L_2Cu-H_2O]^+$, $[L_2Cu-(C_6H_5+FC_6H_4OCH_3+4H)]^+$, $LCuH^+$, $(LCu-H)^+$, $(LCu-CH_2)^+$, $[LCu-(CH_2CO+H_2O)]^+$ and $(LCu-C_6H_5)^+$ ions containing copper. In this compound, we have also noticed a hydrogen atom transfer from the ortho position of phenyl ring, in the formation of $LCuH^+$ ion. Similar observation has been clarified by mass spectral studies of partially deuterated β -diketonates¹¹. The transition $[L_2Cu-(C_6H_5+FC_6H_4OCH_3)]^+ \rightarrow LCuH^+$ has been confirmed by observation of a metastable peak. In the mass spectrum of this compound, peaks due to H_2L^+ , HL and L^+ are also prominent after the

TABLE—1 RELATIVE INTENSITIES OF IONS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF COPPER 1, 3-DIKETONATES*.

Compound No. Ions	1		2		3		4		5		6		7	
	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)	m/e	Int. (%)
L ₂ Cu. ⁺	565	22.8	589	11.4	457	18.0	481	22.0	665	17.5	629	14.0	605	1.6
[L ₂ Cu-H ₂ O]. ⁺	—	—	571	0.4	—	—	463	1.0	647	4.2	611	0.3	587	0.1
[L ₂ Cu-F]. ⁺	546	0.4	570	0.2	—	—	—	—	646	1.1	610	0.7	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-CFO]. ⁺	518	0.8	542	0.8	—	—	—	—	618	0.6	582	0.5	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-R]. ⁺	496	12.5	520	3.0	442	8.0	466	1.6	546	18.5	510	13.0	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-CO]. ⁺	—	—	—	—	429	1.0	453	0.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-Ar]. ⁺	452	0.3	—	—	344	0.1	356	0.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-2R]. ⁺	427*	8.4	451*	2.7	427	1.5	451	0.7	427	12.6	391	12.0	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-COCHCOR]. ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
or LCuAr. ⁺	427*	8.4	451*	2.7	373	2.0	397	1.2	477	0.2	441	0.4	—	—
[L ₂ Cu-(2R+CO)]. ⁺	—	—	—	—	399	1.1	423	0.7	—	—	—	—	—	—
LCu. ⁺	314	0.9	326	3.0	260	8.0	272	10.2	364	0.7	346	1.4	344	0.7
[L ₂ Cu-HL]. ⁺	313	0.8	325	3.6	259	3.0	271	7.4	363	0.7	345	1.0	343	1.7
[LCuH]. ⁺	315	0.6	327	3.6	261	10.5	273	13.6	365	0.4	347	1.3	335	1.0
[LCu-H. O]. ⁺	296	3.0	308	0.1	242	15.0	254	0.2	346	1.4	328	0.1	—	—
[LCu-F]. ²⁺	295	5.5	307	0.2	241	18.0	253	0.2	345	3.3	327	0.3	—	—
[LCu-Ph]. ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	257	—
[LCu-HF]. ⁺	294	5.6	306	0.1	240	21.0	252	0.2	344	2.3	—	—	—	—
HL. ⁺	252	3.0	264	9.6	198	39.0	210	41.6	302	1.8	284	1.7	272	36.0
L. ⁺	251	8.5	263	16.8	197	45.0	209	70.4	301	6.3	283	10.0	271	31.7
[L ₂ Cu-R]. ²⁺	248	1.8	260	0.8	221	0.1	233	0.8	273	0.3	255	0.8	—	—
[LCu-R]. ⁺	245	33.6	257	11.5	245	21.0	257	6.4	245	41.8	277	30.0	—	—
[L-F]. ⁺	232	3.6	244	0.1	178	15.0	190	7.0	282	2.1	264	0.1	—	—
[L-CO]. ⁺	223	0.1	235	2.2	169	0.4	181	3.0	273	0.4	255	0.8	243	1.0
[L-2CO]. ⁺	195	1.9	207	2.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
[L-OF]. ⁺	197	0.6	209	0.6	—	—	—	—	247	19.8	229	15.0	—	—
[L-R]. ⁺	182	6.0	194	0.5	182	0.1	194	1.2	182	0.4	164	0.3	194	0.9
CuAr. ⁺	176	2.3	188	4.1	176	5.0	188	16.0	176	0.7	158	1.8	—	—
[ArCOCH] or [L-COR]	155	0.2	166	2.2	154	0.5	166	1.2	154	2.1	136	2.0	—	—
[ArCOC].	154	1.0	165	0.3	153	1.3	165	1.0	153	0.3	135	0.2	165	0.9
[HL-CHCOR]	142	8.5	154	12.0	142	10.5	154	10.5	142	8.7	124	8.0	—	—
[L-CHCOR]. ⁺	141	100.0	153	100.0	141	100.0	153	100.0	141	100.0	123	100.0	153	100.0
[COCHCOR]	138	1.0	138	1.6	84	0.5	84	1.0	88	0.1	88	0.1	—	—
Ar. ⁺	113	17.8	125	4.8	113	30.0	125	6.4	113	14.6	95	18.0	125	7.6
[Ar-HF]. ⁺	93	1.0	105	2.5	93	3.0	105	1.7	93	0.8	75	2.5	105	0.7
CF ₃ CO. ⁺	97	0.1	97	1.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
C ₂ F ₅ CO. ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	147	0.1	147	0.3	—	—
CH ₃ CO. ⁺	—	—	—	—	43	48.0	43	25.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
CuOAr. ⁺	204	0.6	216	0.3	204	0.9	216	0.2	204	0.3	186	0.3	—	—
CuOCH ₃ . ⁺	93	1.0	93	0.5	93	3.0	93	0.7	93	0.8	93	0.2	93***	1.5
CuCH ₃ . ⁺	77	0.1	77	3.6	77	1.5	77	5.0	77	0.4	77	0.2	77	75.0
CuCH. ⁺	76	0.1	76	1.0	76	0.5	76	1.0	76	0.3	76	0.5	76	5.0
CuC. ⁺	75	1.0	75	2.2	75	7.0	75	2.8	75	0.7	75	2.5	75	7.3
Cu. ⁺	63	4.8	63	3.2	63	12.0	63	2.6	63	7.0	63	3.9	63	6.0

*Only ions containing ⁶³Cu are listed.

**The m/e values for LCuAr.⁺ ion (in cases of compound No. 1 and 2) are same as the m/e values of (L₂Cu-2R)+ion.

***In Compound No. 7 the values in bracket are due to unsubstituted phenyl group.

****The m/e value of Ph.⁺ ion (in case of compound No. 7) is the same as the m/e value of CuCH₃.⁺ ion.

TABLE—2 METASTABLE PEAKS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF COPPER 1, 3-DIKETONATES (Fig. 1)

Sl. No.	Transitions	Compd. No.	m ₁	m ₂	M=(m ₂) ² /m ₁	
					Calc.	obs.
1.	(L ₂ Cu-CF ₃). ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-2CF ₃). ⁺	1	496	427	367.6	368.0
		2	520	451	391.2	391.5
2.	(L ₂ Cu). ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-CF ₃). ⁺	1	565	496	435.5	435.5
3.	(L ₂ Cu-C ₂ F ₅). ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-2C ₂ F ₅). ⁺	5	546	427	333.9	334.0
		6	510	391	299.7	300.0
4.	(L ₂ Cu-CH ₃). ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-2CH ₃). ⁺	4	257	242	227.9	228.0
5.	L ₂ Cu. ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-HL). ⁺ + HL	4	481	271	252.7	252.5
6.	LCuCF ₃ . ⁺ → CuCF ₃ + L. ⁺	1	383	251	164.5	164.5
7.	ArCO. ⁺ → Ar + CO	1	141	113	90.5	90.5
		2	153	125	102.1	102.5
		3	141	113	90.5	90.5
		4	153	125	102.1	102.5
		5	141	113	90.5	90.5
		6	123	95	73.1	73.5
		7	153	125	102.1	102.1
8.	[L ₂ Cu-(C ₆ H ₅ +FC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃). ⁺ → LCuH. ⁺	7	420	335	267.2	267.0
9.	L ₂ Cu. ⁺ → (L ₂ Cu-C ₂ F ₅). ⁺	5	665	546	448.3	448.5
10.	(COCH ₂ COC ₂ F ₅ -2F). ⁺ → (COCHCOC ₂ F ₅ -CFO). ⁺	6	151	141	131.6	131.5

Scheme - B

peak). Similar observation has been reported by Reichert *et al*¹¹ in the case of dibenzoylmethane chelates of Cu(II) and Ni(II).

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